

HISTORY OF LANDSCAPE IN MIDDLE ASIAN WORKS OF ART, PHILOSOPHICAL AND AESTHETIC METHODOLOGY OF EDUCATIONAL PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

R. Jalilova

Senior teacher of the Department of Arts of FarSU, member of the creative association of artists of the Academy Arts of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article deals with art, painting, pencil drawing, composition, the history of the landscape of Europe, Uzbekistan and the work of the famous creative artists were analyzed. The landscape of the painting was interpreted in the philosophical ideas of aesthetic education. The fundamentals of the metaphysics of the reflection of the creative technologies of the new work are discussed.*

Keywords: *ancient architecture, world, east, wall painting, flowers, artist, natural world, nature, mountain, village, city view, warm and cold tones, intervals, color philosophy, mood, world, progress of science.*

Landscape (landscape) is an image of a certain place. In the landscape, people's feelings are expressed in artistic images through the image of nature - the view of the sea, groves, hills, cities and villages, and the image of various places in general. The landscape flourished in China in the Middle Ages, and in Europe during the Renaissance in Japan. In Uzbekistan, U.Tansikboev is famous for his attractive works in the landscape genre.

In the ancient East, the genre of landscape was depicted in a strictly certain order, subject to the laws of the slave society. In ancient Egyptian art, landscape composition began to be used in even more unique styles. Linear size, color and tone relationships have been elevated to a higher level.

The artists of the ancient world began to understand the concepts of symmetry and rhythm in their works, understanding the laws and styles of composition in the succession of leaves and flowers of plants and seasons.

During this period, attention to art was strong. He also showed the aesthetic and ideological views of the people of that time.

The luxurious palaces and temples built during this period, the pictures of life on their walls, vividly reflected the life of the country, expressing the ideology of the time.

According to historical sources, it is noteworthy that the Chinese historian was impressed by the magnificent building built between Samarkand and Bukhara, the northern wall of the building was painted with the image of the Chinese Empire, the eastern wall was painted with Turkish Khans and Indian rulers, and the western wall was painted with the images of Iranian and Roman emperors. The folk art of carving, patterns, woodcarving, relief images and wall pictures gave the building a special charm.

These palaces, which have come down to us in ruins, are still awe-inspiring with their magnificence.

The houses of the nobles in Panjikent were very ornate, especially the corridors leading to the inn and the house. Murals are colorful and depict legendary events, religious ceremonies, and Sogdian feudal lords. There are also pictures dedicated to the legendary courage of Rustam.

In 1965, the discovery of the remains of the legendary king Afrosiyab's palace near Samarkand caused a great stir. The composition of thematic pictures and patterns on the walls of the remains of this palace impresses one with a high level of skill.

When thinking about the monumental decorative paintings of the early feudalism of Central Asia, one cannot help but remember the "Ajina tepa" mural paintings of Uzbekistan and southern Tajikistan found in Vakhsh, and the "Bolalik tepa" mural paintings found near Termiz.

In the first century of feudalism, figurative events were expressed in practical art, objects, weapons, commissioned images, wall paintings.

In the 7th-8th centuries, when the Arabs entered the Central Asian lands, the cultural and artistic works reached the ruins of the monuments, but they could not stop the creativity of the people. In the 9th-10th centuries, Central Asia began to gain independence again. There was a revival in fine and applied arts, and rare monuments began to appear in architecture.

By this time, Central Asia became one of the important centers in the development of world science.

During this period, he delivered to the world a number of scientists who, with their work and intelligence, gave a new direction to the development of world science. They invented new aspects of it and gave it life.

The immortal works of Abu Ali ibn Sina served as textbooks in many educational institutions of the country for several centuries.

The materialistic worldview in the work of a number of thinkers such as Al-Beruni, Al-Farabi, and Al-Farghani influenced the public consciousness.

By this time, great changes took place in architecture. The wide use of brick in construction gave opportunities to create complex architectural compositions. During this period, the tendency to build curved roofs, domed buildings, different types of bricks, and to create a unique decoration of the building wall increased. It is mentioned that there were dome mosques related to Islam during this period.

The rarest monument of this period is the Somonites mausoleum.

This mausoleum is considered a rare monument of world architecture. The external wall surface of the building is artistically decorated with various layers of baked brick.

The building, which looks a bit gloomy, seems to keep an extremely quiet and gloomy silence for those who sleep forever.

In social life, the art of color and engraving began to occupy a wide place.

In addition to various geometric shapes, painters used in their creations patterns with images of plants, animals and birds.

During this period, the palaces and houses of rulers, and the walls of hotels were decorated with pictures in the art of painting and miniature art, written sources.

The story of the painting of the portrait of Abu Ali Ibn Sina, the great scholar of the East, also illustrates the existence of fine art in this period.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina, the king of this period, Mahmud Ghaznavi, could not bear his whims and fled from his palace. When the king found out about this, he ordered Abu Nasr-bin Afon to paint his portrait and other artists to send copies of these portraits to the neighboring countries.

The architectural culture grew in the XI-XII centuries. The Somani dynasty was replaced by the Turkic Karakhanid and Seljuk dynasty.

During this period, the construction of the minaret became a widespread habit. The tallest tower in Central Asia is the Jarkurgan minaret, which amazes people with its height and beauty.

Information about the visual arts of Central Asia. By the end of the 13th century and the 14th-15th centuries, the art of painting developed.

From this period, some original manuscripts, remains of murals and miniatures have reached us.

It is noted that the art of "painting" flourished during the period of Timur and Timurids. It is reported that the walls of the palace near Samarkand built by Temur were painted with battle compositions depicting his bravery in battle, and the walls of the observatory built by Ulugbek were decorated with paintings depicting natural scenes.

The culture of Central Asia, Middle East, book decoration, calligraphy and miniature art is distinguished in history by its unique irrevocable charm.

A major representative of Middle Eastern miniature art is Kamoliddin Bekhzod.

He was born in Khirot (1455-1535). Here Alisher Navoi attracted attention with his talent in painting. Later, under his patronage, he rose to the level of a great artist. One of his famous works during the development of his work is the portrait of Shaibani Khan.

In the middle of the 17th century, a number of artists from Central Asia, such as Davlat Muhammad, Nadir Muhammad, Samarkandi, created in the Baburi palace of India.

Miniatures and murals have been painted since the 17th-19th centuries.

In the 50s and 70s, U.Tansikbaev, who created landscapes in Uzbekistan, R. Temurov created a series of architectural scenes of Samarkand, U.Tansikbaev, "Issyk kol", "Motherland", "Qairakum reservoir", "N.Karakhan", "Nanay yoli", "Spring in Sijjak".

Artists such as R.Choriev, K.Bogodukhov, M.Esin, Pudovkin G.Abdurahmonov, F.Tokhirov in 70-80 years created effectively in the landscape genre. Currently, many sought-after talented artists, A.Nurritdinov, O.Kazokov, Islomshikov, A.Mominov, A.Mirsoatov, etc. have been creating charming landscapes praising the beautiful nature of independent Uzbekistan.

The works of European, Russian, and Uzbek artists who work in the landscape genre.

Landscape is one of the ancient genres of fine art, and the medium plays an important role as a background in historical household works. In ancient Chinese art, artists created works depicting nature. The history of the landscape genre in Europe developed in the 16th and 17th centuries. Dutch landscape painters have achieved great success in realistic depiction of nature.

The development of the landscape genre in Russia dates back to the 18th century. Architectural monuments of Moscow, Petersburg F.E. Skillfully illustrated by Alekseev. Landscape art has the power to positively affect a person by reflecting the beauty of the outside world. Therefore, the artist expresses his aesthetic attitude towards nature, understanding the most delicate, typical situations, color harmonies of the natural world.

In the landscape work, the human personality, intelligence, and inner feelings are sung through images and an image of nature is created. As an example, I. Levitan's "Golden Autumn", "Over the Eternal Silence", I.Shishkin, "Forest Distances", V. Meshkov's "Thoughts about the Urals" can be cited.

The works of the landscape genre in visual arts form the love of nature and the qualities of beauty in a person. In works on historical and domestic themes, artists refer directly to the

landscape, write etudes and sketches. In this case, the landscape serves as an additional background in the picture.

E.Vasnetsov's "Alyonushka" is an example of this. Artists such as K.Yuon, G.Nissky also depicted the natural beauty and modern changes in their works.

In the 50s and 70s, U.Tansikboev, who created landscapes in Uzbekistan, created a series of architectural landscapes of Samarkand, U.Tansikboev, "Hosting lake", "Mother country", Qairokkum reservoir, N. Karakhan, "Nanay yoli", spring in Sijjak, R. Temurov. G. Abdurahmonov, F. Tokhirov in 70-80 years. Artists such as R. Choriev, K. Bogodukhov, M. Esin, created effectively in the landscape genre. Currently, many sought-after talented artists, A.Nuritdinov, O.Kazokov, Islamshikov, A.Mominov, A.Mirsoatov, etc. have been creating charming landscapes praising the beautiful nature of independent Uzbekistan.

There are several types of landscape. City (Architecture), rural (mountain) landscape, industrial (factory, factory, construction), historical, romantic, lyrical, panoramic (view) landscapes are among them.

At the base of each of these lies the content, the idea. Cityscapes are examples of city life, architecture, vehicles, people, parks, and underpasses.

The composition is based on the image of rural landscape, vast expanse, mountain landscape, pastures, rocks, plants, sparkling water in the valley. The art scene is connected with a large factory yard, reservoir, bridge, subway construction, and construction equipment.

In the lyrical landscape, we bring before our eyes a work on themes such as "Early Morning", "Spring", which reflects the subtle, quiet beauty of nature, its state of awakening, and which gives a person universal joy. Composition tools (signs) of the landscape; These include location, point of view, line of sight, spatial distance, format, perspective, rhythm, color, light, reflex, compositional center.

In summary Central Asia, the history of the landscape genre, artistic works, philosophical and aesthetic methods of education, problems and solutions, scientific classification were studied.

Creative pedagogic training of young people is considered to be the basis of specialized disciplines of elementary painting, composition, pencil drawing, and painting. A young creative student should have excellent knowledge. A student will gain skills by scientifically analyzing the works of European, Russian and Uzbek artists who create in the landscape genre. Painting, drawing, composition images, creative skills of young people are developed by practical training. If we want to describe the composition of urban architecture landscape and situation, first of all, it is necessary to carefully observe the characteristic features of sunny, cloudy days, noon, and evening in nature. A line of color drawn from nature can be the main theme in composing an early morning landscape composition.

It is necessary to determine the format of the image, determine the horizon line, the point of view. Then it is necessary to determine the proportions of the air and the ground on the plane, find the foreground, the background and the scale of the objects. If you have several options for the composition, it is recommended to perform it on soft materials such as coal.

Depicting the version of the completed rough sketch in color will help determine the color of the work.

On the basis of a qualitatively executed sketch, the final version of the landscape composition should be made in practice. It is done using paper, cardboard, canvas, watercolor,

gouache, watercolor. For a future artist, observing life, making daily sketches and sketches on the subject will be a good thing if he starts doing exercises. Works in the landscape genre provide spiritual nourishment for a person, inspire him, bring happiness and joy to life.

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